

A Study On Employee Satisfaction In Turning Point Consultancy Services

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ABSTRACT

Job Satisfaction among TPCS Employees is the Topic of the Current Study. The primary purpose of the study was to assess the level of contentment felt by members of the organization. Customer service is crucial to the growth of any company.

Workers' happiness on the job depends on a wide variety of variables, including but not limited to their salary, their ability to create meaningful work, the quality of their working environment, and many more. The questionnaire was the main tool for gathering information. The majority of the secondary data came from published articles, while the remainder came from business databases and online repositories. The information was gathered by distributing a standardized questionnaire to the workforce. The data was dissected using a random number generator.

From the administration of the questionnaire early that morning until the presentation of the results, conclusions, and recommendations, the utmost care has been taken. The study must conclude that the employees' level of maturity is adequate.

Discontent was also expressed with respect to a few of the causes. It was planned that if employees are unhappy, it would have a negative impact on the association's performance and output. In addition, helpful ideas and suggestions are provided to improve the company's future prospects.

Keywords: ANOVA test, Correlation, Regression, interpretation.

I. OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

In this study, there are roughly three(3) exploration objects used as a guideline for the Research to work on. The objects were on relating the workers job satisfaction. Below in the specific objects used as reference in this study

1. To understand the relationship between the workers and operation of the association.
2. To identify the difference between Expectation & Perception of the workers from the association regarding payment, working condition, installation handed etc.
3. To identify the hand ' satisfaction position toward association.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The human resources management is that the term accustomed describe the staff within the organization where the organization has 3 responsibility that area unit staffing, worker compensation and benefits and coming up with work to follow for the event of the organization. it's vital role within the organization to avoid shortage of human resources management. Nguyen Ngoc Thang (2012), has analysed that the Vietnam Company suffers from shortage of human resources. So, the corporate ought to improve HRM for the advantages of the full Vietnam. It should implement higher reward, selection, coming up with and appraisal for rising the HRM.

Performance of the worker depicts employee's potential and their ability of labor they will do. Performance of the worker are paid consequently to their performance of the work. On the off probability that they worker performance additional it influence the worker performance connected pay. Patrick L. O'Halloran, (2012) has analyzed the performance connected pay influences the employee turnover. It provides additional empirical support for the sorting model of Performance Related Pay than the classic organization model. moreover, staff acceptive some sort of Performance connected Pay area unit less probably to prevent and area unit well less probably to be forsaking than those not obtaining any sort of Performance connected Pay. It reveals negative relationship between a total live of Performance connected Pay and turnover and moreover there's a negative relationship between share and turnover.

Job satisfaction clarifies regarding what proportion a representative consummated of doing job within the association with the various ways that enclosed like their sentiments, conduct, intrigue. At the purpose once

there is increment within the execution, its outcome job satisfaction of the employee in lightweight of the actual fact that with no intrigue or satisfaction a representative cannot execution it well. Xiao-Hong subgenus Chen, Ke Zhao, Xiang Liu, Desheng Dash Shanghai dialect, (2012), say that the instrument through that incorporating and dialogue peace promotion practices area unit emphatically connected on job satisfaction.

Incorporating peace promotion conduct is decidedly known with advancement execution and keeping removed from deciding conduct is contrarily known with development execution.

Motivating staff within the association is to expand the potency and find better of their capability as a yield. player H Porter, Kelly Diane Riesenmy, Dail Eireann Fields, (2016), as stony-broke down the employee inspiration to steer for associate degree association must acknowledge the chance for improvement as authoritative pioneers. the standard of relationship differs among the 3 elective styles of administration inspiration. For deciding employee MTL worker appraisals of pay, advancement openings, acknowledgment, work define, nature of authoritative correspondences, and work environment deep sense of being assume an essential half.

The new staff have to be compelled to apprehend basic data of their leader. this offers the positive relationship to the firm performance. For job satisfactorily the coaching programs area unit used train new worker for the essential information. Sohyoun Synthia Shin, Sungho Lee (2016), say that the client Orientation (CO), competition Orientation (PO) and Technology Orientation (TO) certainly impact originality, contributing the companies performance.

Hour strategy is regarding the duty during which the association ensures that they meet their objectives, mission, and future wants of the organization. Jane Frances Maley, (2011), has announced that the Human quality strategy used by a transnational organization considerably affects the explanation and agreeableness of the full execution administration method. It adds to a more full comprehension of the impact of strategy on execution administration, which is distinguished as an important procedure for authoritative aggressiveness. It to boot speaks to associate degree important advance within the improvement of universal business explore.

The employee positive health care that depicts regarding the work and non-work regions. Where there is positive health comes regarding there's a superior worker work execution. In turns positive health care the association gets additional elevated quantity of employment fulfilment and execution.

Lauren J. Davenport, et.al (2016), says that there's heaps of scholastic writing that supporters the utilization of positive work place rehearses. This influences a 1 of a sort commitment to the work to place psychological eudaemonia by covering the development rules that centres around advancing positive emotional well-being within the work place. Altogether, 220/278 techniques were appraised as basic or crucial by no but eighty for each penny of the 2 boards.

Engagement of the worker within the organisation with the total potential and interest there's positive results of their performance and advantage of the organisation. Lisa E. Baranik, Lillian Eby, (2016), has found that the workers have interaction in serving to behaviours at work, positive have an effect on might develop & workers could reap advantages that area unit related to high positive effects. Managers will boost OCB-Is by aggressively opposing rudeness among employees and praising those who take part in social events at work. High levels of job satisfaction, fairness, and structural commitment, as well as low levels of role ambiguity and role conflict, are associated with OCB-Is in the workplace.

Another paper that studied the support of the organisation on the worker performance,

found the perception within the organisation is that the workers believes within the well being of the organisation and fulfilment of their emotional wants and social support. Owais Nazir, Jamid UIslam (2017), has analysed that the perceived structure support on worker performance and affectional commitment area unit completely unconcealed. it's been mediate by worker engagement.

Motivating the worker by the pioneers is to expand their execution and their duty towards the workplace they work. Knowing the workers can supply attempt to pioneer key to evoke them within the way they're. Michael C. Sturman, Henry M. Robert Ford (2011), say that the main key to inspiration is to consider their workers. The friendliness workers hunt for occupations that area unit reasonable, fun, fascinating, and imperative. It acknowledges initiative by chiefs WHO will figure out what each individual is sorting out within the work relationship and might provides it dependably and decently. It in addition offers authority that takes the time and endeavours to ensure that employees area unit appropriately treated, paid, regarded, and perceived. The lure is that everybody's that means of cheap, fun, intriguing, essential, and properly oversight is exclusive.

To analyse the matter that have an effect on the worker works within the work place. The difficulties arise when

there's distinction within the demographical space that affects the work perception. When the employee apprehend the work and perceive the work won't have an effect on the work and work place.

Tachia Chin, Ren-huai Liu (2015), say that Employees are most likely to complain about issues related to "harmony with corporate system," "harmony across departments," and "harmony with firm leader," respectively. Workers' opinions of workplace harmony are shown to vary according to a number of demographic factors, including age, gender, legal status, educational level, tenure, and position. Clash, compromise, communication, consensus, and conflict model area unit supported. Employee consummated once they area unit creating the foremost of their work. The impact of the worker satisfaction is by the low persuading in their commitment, elite however no analysis this components can have an effect on the worker satisfaction. Sandra Brunia, et.al (2016), has unconcealed that worker satisfaction is wedged by varied physical qualities of the geographic point and by the execution procedure. Satisfaction with the association has a sway too.

The problems arise within the organisation once workers profit of their work. The negotiation behaviour of {the worker|the worker} area unit disagree or discontented with the opposite employee the problems arises. Aukje Nauta, Karin Sanders, (2000), as aforementioned that the negotiation behaviour specifically, the problem-solving approach—was a lot of possible once people were extrovertive and agreeable, once workers perceived high interdepartmental reciprocity, and when organizations didn't have a affordable strategy. Battling was a lot of probable once folks were extraverted and repulsive, and yielding was nearly sure once workplace people saw an influence advantage opposite the opposite division. It offers direction to associations in their endeavors to support valuable exchange conduct between offices..

To analyse the Organisational trust and worker data, wherever there's confidence of the employee towards the performance that area unit useful. the talents of the worker data on their job area unit made public with their duties within which they believe on the work they are doing and result can be favour on them. Herbaceous Plant, Heidi Olander, and Mika Vanhala According to Hurmelinna-Laukkanen and Kirsimarja Blomqvist (2016), companies will use both formal and informal employee-related mechanisms to deal with data leaky and theft. trust in the underlying structure has a multiplicative effect on the prevalence of employee-related practices that mitigate data theft, and this effect holds true across all forms.

Examining how contentment with responsibility coaching relates to feelings about one's employment and the likelihood that one may quit. When the trainee is engaged and satisfied with their training. Coaching can improve job fulfillment. The relationship between job coaching satisfaction, job satisfaction, and turnover intent is investigated by Wen-Rou Huang and Chih-Hao Su (2016). As a mediator, job satisfaction is discovered to have a negative role in the association between satisfaction with job coaching and intention to leave the company. The satisfaction with the coach's performance on the job will be used to make predictions about employees' likelihood of leaving for greener pastures. In addition, job satisfaction is positively related to commitment to remaining in the position, but it is inversely related to a desire to leave.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research design:

Data collection techniques:

The information was collected from primary & secondary sources.

Primary Data: Interference of experimenter in the filling out of questionnaires to gather data from workers.

Secondary Data:

Apart from primary data, We collect data from textbooks, Journals, & use of internet is used for the study.

Sampling:

- a. **Population Size: 100**
- b. **Sampling Design:** Purposive Sampling
- c. **Techniques:** Correlation, ANOVA and Regression

Sample Size:

Out of all, maximum, 60 - 70% sampling will be taken

Research Factors

1. Employees Satisfaction (Dependent)

1. Salary Paid(Independent)
2. Work balance(Independent)
3. Promotion opportunity(Independent)
4. Team Work(Independent)
5. Motivation(Independent)
6. Performance Appraisal(Independent)
7. Rules and Regulation(Independent)

Figure 1

Table 1 Gender

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 1.0	80	80.0	80.0	80.0
2.0	20	20.0	20.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

From the above graph shows that 79.2% respondents are **Male** and 20% are **Female**.

Figure 2

Table 2. Age

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 1.0	13	13.0	13.0	13.0
2.0	42	53.0	42.0	66.0
3.0	38	26.0	38.0	92.0
4.0	7	8.0	7.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

From the above graph shows that 53% respondents belongs to 21-30 years of age group, 26.7% of respondent are from 31-40 years , 13.3% is from 1-20 years age group rest remaining is above 41-50 years.

Figure 3

From the above graph shows that 60% respondent belongs to **HSC**, 26% respondents belongs to **Graduation**, 10% respondents belongs to **SSLC** and 4% respondents belong to **PG**.

Table 3 Educational Qualification

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 1.0	7	7.0	7.0	7.0
2.0	48	60.0	60.0	67.0
3.0	39	26.0	26.0	93.0
4.0	6	7.0	7.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Figure 4

Table 4 Occupation

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 1.0	80	80.0	80.0	80.0
3.0	20	20.0	20.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

From the above graph shows that 80% respondent belongs to **salaried**, 20% respondents belongs to **Professional**.

Figure 5

Table 5 Your Status

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 1.0	39	47.0	47.0	47.0
2.0	61	53.0	53.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

From the above graph shows that 53.3% respondent belongs to **Married**, remaining 46.7% respondents belongs to **Unmarried**.

Figure 6

Table 6 Your family Type

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 1.0	80	73.0	73.0	73.0
2.0	20	27.0	27.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

From the above graph shows that 73.3% respondent belongs to **Nuclear family** and 26.7% respondents belongs to **Joint Family**.

Figure 7

Table 7 Size of the family

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 1.0	7	6.0	6.0	6.0
2.0	78	73.0	73.0	85.0
3.0	8	13.0	13.0	96.0
4.0	7	4.0	4.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

The above graph shows that 73.3% respondents have 3-6 Members, 13.3% respondent have 7-9 members in the family, 4% respondents are above 9 members **in a family**, and remaining 6% family have 3 Members in family.

Figure 8

Table 8 Children

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 1.0	13	20.0	20.0	20.0
2.0	29	33.0	33.0	42.0
3.0	25	13.0	13.0	66.0
4.0	33	34.0	34.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

The data above reveals that one-third of respondents has 2 kids in their household, one-third do not, 13% have even more than two children, and the remaining 20% have just one kid.

Figure 9

Table 9 Whether any other family member is working

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 1.0	19	20.0	20	20
2.0	81	80.0	80	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

From the above graph shows that 80% respondents only Father is a working Member andin 20% respondent says that Spouse is a working person in Family.

Figure 10

Table 10 Annual Income

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 1.0	18	20	20	20
2.0	51	60	60	80
3.0	25	13	13	93.0
4.0	6	7	7	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

The above graph shows that 60% of respondents belong to 1-2 Lakhs, 20% of respondent

are form Below 1 Lakh, 13.3% respondent are from 2-3 Lakhs, and rest 7% of respondent belong to Above 3 Lakh category.

Figure 11

Table 11 Do you have any vehicle

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 1.0	67	67	67.0	67.0
2.0	6	6.0	6.0	73.0
3.0	27	27.0	27.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

The above graph shows that 66.7% of respondents have Two Wheeler and 26.7% of respondent don't have any vehicle, and remaining 6.6% of respondent have Four Wheeler.

Figure 12

Table 12 You stay in

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 1.0	41	32.0	32.0	32.0
2.0	59	68.0	68.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

The above graph shows that 68.2% of respondents stay in Rented House and remaining 31.8% of respondent stayin their Own House.

Figure 13

Table 13 Region

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1.0	60	60.0	60.0	60.0
	2.0	26	26.0	26.0	86.0
	3.0	7	7.0	7.0	93.0
	4.0	7	7.0	7.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

The above graph shows that 60% respondents belongs to North Region, 26.7% respondent belong to South Region, 4% respondents are above 9 members **in a family**, and remaining 6%family have 3 Members in family.

Figure 14

Table 14 Overall Satisfaction

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1.0	4	4.0	4.0	4.0
	2.0	14	14.0	14.0	18.0
	3.0	40	40.0	40.0	58.0
	4.0	38	38.0	38.0	96.0
	5.0	4	4.0	4.0	100.0
	Total		100	100.0	100.0

The above graph shows that 21% respondents are experienced between **0-2 Years**, 38% respondent are experienced between **2-4 Years**. 32% respondents are experienced between **4-6 Years**, 4% respondents are experienced between **8-10 Years** and 2% respondents are experienced between **8-10 Years**

Figure 15

Table 15 Ability to balance work with their personal life

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1.0	3	3.8	3.8	3.8
	2.0	9	9.4	9.4	13.2
	3.0	45	45.3	45.3	58.5
	4.0	35	34	34	92.5
	5.0	8	7.5	7.5	100.0
	Total		100	100.0	100.0

The above graph shows that 45% of respondent are moderately satisfied with the work and personal life balance, 34% of respondents are just satisfied and 7.5% of respondent are strongly satisfied with the work and personal life balance.

Figure 16

Table 16 Chance to learn new.

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 1.0	2	2.0	2.0	2.0
2.0	14	15	15	17.0
3.0	50	47.2	47.2	64.2
4.0	28	28.3	28.3	92.5
5.0	6	7.5	7.5	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

The above graph shows that 47% of respondent are neutral and say that have chance to learn new but 2% of respondents are dissatisfied, just 7.5% of respondent are extremely delighted and remaining 28.3% of employees are satisfied and say that have chance to learn new

Figure.17

Table 17 Facilities Provided

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 1.0	3	3.8	3.8	3.8
2.0	12	9.4	9.4	15.0
3.0	55	56.6	56.6	70.0
4.0	27	26.4	26.4	97.0
5.0	3	3.8	3.8	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

The above graph shows that 3.8% of respondent are Dissatisfied, 9.4% of respondents are poorly satisfied, 56.6% of respondent are Neutral, 26.4% of respondent are satisfied and remaining 3.8% are extremely delighted with the facilities provided to them.

Figure 18

Table 18 Management problem solving.

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 2.0	12	12.0	12.0	12.0
3.0	54	54.0	54.0	66.0
4.0	33	33.0	33.0	99.0
5.0	1	1.0	1.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

The above graph shows that 12% of respondents are poorly satisfied, 54% of respondent are Neutral, 33% of respondent are Satisfied and remaining 1% are extremely delighted with the Management problem solving strategy.

Figure 19

The above graph and downwards table shows that 3.8% of respondent are Dissatisfied, 15.1% of respondents are poorly satisfied, 47.2% of respondent are Neutral, 24.5% of respondent are Satisfied and remaining 9.4% are extremely delighted with Rules and Regulation.

Table 19 Rules and Regulations

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 1.0	3	3.8	3.8	3.8
2.0	18	15.1	15.1	18.9
3.0	44	47.2	47.2	66.1
4.0	27	24.5	24.5	90.6
5.0	8	9.4	9.4	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Figure 20

The above graph and downwards table shows that 1.9% of respondent are Dissatisfied, 48.1% of respondent are Neutral, 36.5% of respondent are Satisfied and remaining 3.9% are extremely delighted with Level of understanding of HR and welfare policy.

Table 20 Level of understanding of HR and welfare poli

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 1.0	3	1.9	1.9	1.9
2.0	11	9.6	9.6	11.5
3.0	51	48.1	48.1	59.6
4.0	32	36.5	36.5	96.1
5.0	3	3.9	3.9	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Figure 21

The data shown in the graph and table above and below indicates that 4 percent of respondents are dissatisfied, 20 percent are badly pleased, 46 percent are neutral, 25 percent are content, and 5 percent are highly thrilled with the salary they are now receiving.

Table 21 Salary Paid

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 1.0	4	4.0	4.0	4.0
2.0	21	20	20.0	24.0
3.0	47	46	46.0	70.0
4.0	23	25	25	95.0
5.0	5	5	5.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Figure 22

It can be seen from the graph and table above that just 2% of respondents are unhappy with the workplace's current physical state, while 11% are only pleased, 59% are ambivalent, 26% are content, and 2% are overjoyed.

Table 22 Satisfaction In Workplace

	Fre
Valid 1.0	3
2.0	12
3.0	59
4.0	24
5.0	2
Total	100

Figure 23

According to the data shown in the graph and table above, 13% of respondents are dissatisfied with the degree of cooperation across departments, 58% are ambivalent, 23% are content, and the remaining 7% are very satisfied.

Table 23 Satisfaction level regarding co-operation between different departments

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 2.0	12	12.0	12.0	12.0
3.0	61	58.0	58.0	70.0
4.0	21	23.0	23.0	93.0
5.0	6	7	7	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Figure 24

According to the data shown in the graph and table above, 4% of respondents are dissatisfied, 11% are badly pleased, 47% are neutral, 34% are content, and 4% are highly thrilled with their degree of interaction with their peers, superiors, and subordinates.

Table 24 Satisfaction level regarding interpersonal relationship with peers, superiors & subordinates

subordinate

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 1.0	4	4.0	4.0	4.0
2.0	13	11.0	11.0	15.0
3.0	44	47.0	47.0	62.0
4.0	36	34.0	34.0	96.0
5.0	3	4	4	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Figure 25

According to the data shown in the graph and table above, just 2% of respondents are unsatisfied, 15% are only somewhat pleased, 42% are ambivalent, 35% are satisfied, and 6% are very happy with the way superiors evaluate and account for their point of view.

Table 25 The way superior gets respondent's view & take it when making the key decision._

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 1.0	2	2.0	2.0	2.0
2.0	18	15.0	15.0	17.0
3.0	40	42.0	42.0	59.0
4.0	34	35.0	35.0	94.0
5.0	6	6.0	6.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Figure 26

According to the data shown in the graph and table above, just 9.4 percent of respondents are very unhappy with their workplace conditions, while 43.1 percent are lukewarm, 39.5 percent are content, and 39.6 percent are satisfied.

Table 26 To what extent do you agree with the working condition?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 2.0	15	9.4	9.4	9.4
3.0	39	43.4	43.4	52.8
4.0	39	39.6	39.6	92.4
5.0	7	7.6	7.6	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Figure 27

According to the data shown in the graph and table above, just 2% of respondents are "very happy" with the reward plan for their productive labor, while 7.5% are "poorly satisfied."

Table 27 Do you have any incentives wage scheme for efficient work on your organization?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 2.0	7	7.5	7.5	7.0
3.0	59	56.5	56.5	64
4.0	32	34	34	98
5.0	2	2.0	2.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Figure 28

The above graph shows that 74% of respondents say YES that they feel rewarded for their work employee and 20% of respondents say NO but remaining 6% are not sure

Table 28 Performance Appraisal

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 1.0	74	74.0	74.0	74.0
2.0	20	20.0	20.0	94.0
3.0	6	6.0	6.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Figure 29

The above graph shows that 64% of respondents say YES that their opinions are heard and valued by the superior and 34% of respondents say NO but remaining 2% are not sure.

Table 29 Do you feel that your opinions are heard and valued by your superior?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1.0	64	64.0	64.0	64.0
	2.0	34	34.0	34.0	98.0
	3.0	2	2.0	2.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Measurement tools:

In this study we have used SPSS to find out Correlation, Regression and Anova. And these are the statistical tools that could fetch the required answer appropriately.

IV. INTERPRETATION

Correlation

It is possible to quantify the strength of the connection between two variables by using a statistical technique called correlation. Values of the correlation coefficient fluctuate between 1 and -1. Lack of association between two variables, as shown by a correlation coefficient of zero. If the correlation coefficient is -1, then the relationship between the two variables is perfectly negative; a rise in one leads to a decrease in the other. When the correlation between two variables is 1, it signifies that they always and predictably change in tandem.

Correlation:

		Correlations			
		Overall Satisfaction	New Opportunities	Rules and Regulations	Salary Paid
Overall Satisfaction	Pearson Correlation	1	.458**	.470**	.393**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.024	.000	.000
	N	100	100	100	100
New Opportunities	Pearson Correlation	.458**	1	.492**	.540**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.013	.000
	N	100	100	100	100
Rules and Regulations	Pearson Correlation	.470**	.492**	1	.378**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.053
	N	100	100	100	100
Salary Paid	Pearson Correlation	.393**	.540**	.378**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.031	
	N	100	100	100	100

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Interpretation

Overall Satisfaction

- There is a correlation between General Optimism and Job Openings, as seen in the table below. A modest positive connection among Overall Satisfaction & New vacancies is shown by a value of 0.458 between the two variables.
- The following table illustrates the correlation between General Mood and Compliance with Laws and Policies. There is a positive relationship among overall satisfaction & rules and regulations, as shown by a correlation of 0.470 and 1.
- In the table below, we can see a correlation between Total Happiness and Earnings. There is a slight positive relationship among overall satisfaction & salary, as shown by a correlation coefficient of 0.393 and a mean value of 1.

New Opportunities

- The table below shows the correlation between Job Openings and Users' Pleasure with Life in General. There is a modest positive relationship among New openings & Overall Satisfaction, as shown by a correlation of 0.450 to 1. There is a connection among New openings as well as the table's Rules and Regulation column.
- There is a positive relationship among New openings & Rules and Regulation, as measured by a correlation of 0.492 and 1. Table shows a correlation between vacancies and salaries.
- There is a substantial positive relationship among New vacancies and Salary Paid, as shown by a correlation of 0.540 and 1.

Rules and regulation

- The table displays the relationship between Rules and Regulation and Overall Satisfaction. The correlation between Rules and Regulation and Overall Satisfaction is 0.470 and 1 indicating as there's optimistic relationship amongst Rules and Regulation and Overall Satisfaction.
- The table displays the relationship between Rules and Regulation and New openings. The correlation between Rules and Regulation and New openings is 0.492 and 1 indicating as

there's optimistic relationship amongst Rules and Regulation and New openings The table displays the relationship between Rules and Regulation and Salary Paid.

- The correlation between Rules and Regulation and Salary Paid is 0.378 and 1 indicating as there's optimistic relationship amongst Rules and Regulation and Salary Paid

Salary Paid

- The following table illustrates the connection between Total Annual Compensation and Job Satisfaction. Poor positive correlation among salary and job satisfaction is indicated by a value of 0.393 between salary and job satisfaction and 1.
- The chart below shows how vacancies and salaries have changed over time. A positive relationship exists among Salary Paid & New vacancies, as shown by a correlation of 0.540 and 1.
- Compensation received is shown in the table below, along with its correlation to applicable regulations. The 0.378 and 1 connection between Salary Paid & Rules and Regulations provides little evidence of a positive relationship between the two.

Correlations

		Work Balance	Motivation	Performance Appraisal
Work Balance Correlation	Pearson	1	.095	.067
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.348	.506
	N	100	100	100
Motivation Correlation	Pearson	.095	1	.747**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.348		.000
	N	100	100	100
Performance Appraisal Correlation	Pearson	.067	.747**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.506	.000	
	N	100	100	100

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Work Balance

- Work-life equilibrium and perceived challenge are shown in the table below. An insufficiently positive correlation of 0.095 to 1 among Work Balance & provocation suggests that the two are unrelated.
- The following table illustrates the correlation between Work-Life Balance and Performance Reviews. There is a weak positive link among Work Balance & Performance Appraisal, as measured by a coefficient of 0.067 and a mean value of 1.
- Provocation and Work-Life Balance have a weak relationship, as measured by a correlation coefficient of 0.095 and a cutoff of 1.
- Exhibited in the following table is the correlation between Motivation and Performance Evaluation.
- There is a strong positive relationship between Motivation and Performance Appraisal; the correlation between the two is 0.747 and 1.

Correlations

		Team Work	Promotion Opportunity	Job Satisfaction
Team Work	Pearson Correlation	1	.050	.026
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.620	.797
	N	100	100	100
Promotion Opportunity	Pearson Correlation	.050	1	.287**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.620		.004
	N	100	100	100
Job Satisfaction	Pearson Correlation	.026	.287**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.797	.004	
	N	100	100	100

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Platoon work

- As shown by a correlation coefficient of 0.050 between teamwork and promotion prospects, this is a weakly favorable relationship.
- An insignificant positive association of 0.026 between teamwork and job satisfaction may be inferred from this finding.

Promotion Opportunity

- There is a weak positive association between Promotion occurrence and platoon Work (r=0.050 and 1 indicates no correlation), but the two are positively correlated when taken together (r=0.50 and 1 shows excellent correlation).
- The weakly positive correlation of 0.287 between Promotion Occasion and Job Satisfaction suggests that there is no significant relationship between the two.

Job satisfaction

The following table shows the correlation between job contentment and platoon work. In a weakly positive direction, job happiness and team work satisfaction have a correlation of 0.26 and 1, respectively.

The following table illustrates the correlation between Job Satisfaction and Promotion Potential. There is a weak positive association between Job satisfaction and Promotion Opportunity satisfaction (r=0.287 and 1 respectively).

Regression

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.791 ^a	.625	.580	.5794

a. Predictors: (Constant), Promotion Opportunity , Team Work, Facilities Provided , Management problem solving., Motivation, chance to learn new., Rules and Regulations, Work Balance, Performance Appraisal, Salary Paid

Interpretation

The independent variables contribute 62.5% to dependent variable.

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1(Constant)	-.821	.416		-1.973	.052	-1.648	.007
Chance to learn new.	.000	.102	.000	-.001	.999	-.202	.202
Facilities Provided	.465	.107	.405	4.346	.000	.252	.677
Management problem solving.	.726	.115	.517	6.337	.000	.498	.953
Rules and Regulations	.167	.094	.172	1.777	.079	-.020	.354
Salary Paid	-.012	.111	-.012	-.111	.912	-.232	.208
Work Balance	-.136	.111	-.129	-1.230	.222	-.357	.084
Motivation	.333	.168	.202	1.983	.051	-.001	.667

Performance Appraisal	-.172	.164	-.110	-1.050	.297	-.498	.154
Team Work	-.073	.187	-.029	-.390	.697	-.445	.299
Promotion Opportunity	.064	.092	.049	.690	.492	-.120	.247

a. Dependent Variable: Overall Satisfaction

ANOVAa

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	46.444	10	4.644	13.834	.000 ^b
	Residual	27.865	83	.336		
	Total	74.309	93			

a. Dependent Variable: Overall Satisfaction

b. Predictors: (Constant), Promotion Opportunity , Team Work, Facilities Provided ,Management problem solving., Motivation, chance to learn new., Rules and Regulations, Work Balance, Performance Appraisal, Salary Paid

Interpretation

The significance level value is .000 which is less than 0.05. Therefore, we accept the alternate hypothesis and reject the null hypothesis.

ANOVA TEST

The premise that two or more variables are equal is tested through analysis of variance. This compares the relative significance of one or more variables across many levels of analysis. To do an ANOVA analysis, you'll need a response variable and some kind of categorical factor(s) with varying levels of importance. For analysis by means of variance (ANOVA), it is necessary to have data obtained from total strength that are regularly distributed, with equal fluctuations across factor levels.

Analysis of perception about Rules and Regulation, Motivation, Performance Appraisal attraction based on Gender using Anova.

ANOVA

	Sum of Squares		df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Rules and Regulations	Between Groups	2.890	1	2.890	3.433	.067
	Within Groups	82.500	98	.842		
	Total	85.390	99			
Motivation	Between Groups	.722	1	.722	2.581	.111
	Within Groups	27.437	98	.280		
	Total	28.160	99			

Performance Appraisal	Between Groups	.160	1	.160	.467	.496
	Within Groups	33.600	98	.343		
	Total	33.760	99			

INTERPRETATION

The table below displays the responses to the Motivation survey by gender. A p-value of 0.440 indicates that Motivation is significant. This number is higher than 0.111. As a result, we accept the null hypothesis and conclude that there is no gender difference in how Motivation is seen.

H0: The Performance Appraisal is seen the same by both men and women.

H1: Gender has a role in shaping how people of different sexes think about Performance Appraisal.

Level of significance: 0.05

The Performance Appraisal is broken down by gender in the following table. For Performance Appraisal, the p-value is 0.496. This leads us to accept the null hypothesis and draw the conclusion that there is no difference

ANOVA

Sum of Squares			df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Rules and Regulations	Between Groups	2.933	3	.978	1.138	.338
	Within Groups	82.457	96	.859		
	Total	85.390	99			
Motivation	Between Groups	.027	3	.009	.031	.993
	Within Groups	28.133	96	.293		
	Total	28.160	99			
Performance Appraisal	Between Groups	.105	3	.035	.100	.960
	Within Groups	33.655	96	.351		
	Total	33.760	99			

Interpretation:

The following table displays responses to a survey regarding the Performance Appraisal, broken down by age group. Customer satisfaction has a p-value of 0.993, which is statistically significant. In this case, the number over 0.960 is the correct interpretation. In light of this lack of evidence, we accept the null hypothesis and draw no conclusions regarding whether or not there is an age-related variation in how people see Performance Appraisal.

V. FINDINGS

- An analysis of variance (ANOVA) revealed no significant gender differences in responses to questions regarding rules and regulations, prompting, and performance evaluation.
- The results of the ANOVA test showed that there was no significant difference in how the three groups of students perceived the rules and regulations, motivation, and performance evaluation. The analysis of variance showed that there is no difference in how people in different occupations see rules and regulations, motivation, and performance evaluation..
- It was seen from the ANOVA test did that there's no distinction in perceptivity about Rules and Regulation, Motivation and Performance Appraisal grounded on Yearly Income.
- It was seen that 74 of repliers are satisfied and 26 of repliers aren't satisfied regarding terrain at the work place.

- It was seen that 60 of repliers are satisfied and 30 of repliers aren't and remaining 10 responded aren't Sure about Organization fair policy for creation
- It was seen that 84 of repliers satisfied and 16 of repliers aren't satisfied with the Team Support at Work.
- It was seen that 76 of replier are satisfied and 24 of repliers aren't satisfied with the praise or redundant benefit handed to them when they do good work.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

- With the help of our design team, I was able to spend some time with the TPCS Group.
- I was able to better understand how the organization functioned, which aided me in putting our theoretical understanding into practice.
- It is crucial for every organization to know what its employees want and provide it to them before they depart.
- Without action by the association, every organization stands to lose skilled employees to its rivals. Therefore, it is crucial for every organization to guarantee employee happiness. According to the results, the vast majority of employees are pleased with their current positions.
- Workers who have reached their peak working years are content with the union's compensation plan, incentive initiatives, workplace perks, and general treatment.
- They are also pleased with the association's channels of contact and the hand-to-hand interaction with their employers. Nevertheless, just forty of the staff are given voting rights.
- We also hope that the employees' maturity is not predetermined by the weal 72. If the business pays attention to the survey's results and recommendations, the group will be able to increase the quality of their output and increase their sense of accomplishment.

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